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The Reinvention of Learning in A Post Pandemic World: Phygital Learning

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Abstract: Education has been one of the biggest victims of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. A UNICEF-ITU report indicates that this was the largest mass education disruption in modern history, affecting 1.6 billion children worldwide. Challenges arise as we navigate post-COVID 19. The transition will need to be managed through a combination of digital and physical approaches to teaching and learning. This mixed pedagogical mechanism, called phygital, will be the way of the future. Physical education has an opportunity to get rid of the monotony of ordinary school education by reforming education. A new way of delivering education through “blended learning” is a concept that has gained new ground during the pandemic. Blended learning, as we can say, or Phygital Education, in simple words, is a combination of physical learning and digital learning. Educational institutions should embrace this as it provides flexible teaching and learning in the new world we are entering.

Keywords: COVID-19, Digital learning, Post-COVID, Inclusive learning

1.1 Background of the Study

The world is facing the current realities of the coronavirus pandemic, the outbreak of which has not spared public efforts, institutions, and even education. The crippled human activity, effort and economy of the world as a result of the coronavirus pandemic came as a rude shock as there was no canary in the coal mine to offer something of this magnitude. In this regard, this paper reviews the current state of the coronavirus pandemic, highlights a clear transition from the COVID-19 era to the post-COVID era, and makes some recommendations that can help the Nigerian government or other educational authorities. As emphasized, governments and stakeholders must ensure equity in closing the educational disparity by providing adequate funding for the education and teacher training (and retraining) sector, and finally by creating an enabling environment for both students and teachers. prosper.

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused dramatic and profound changes around the world. Economic crises within countries and around the world are likely to lead to fiscal austerity, increased poverty and reduced resources available for investment in public services, both through domestic spending and development assistance. All of this will lead to a human development crisis that will continue long after the transmission of the disease has stopped.

Quarantine has accelerated the introduction of digital technologies. Business centers, educational institutes, analytics, computers, data management methods and online education solutions have been forced to work in tandem and improve quality and delivery times to cope with such situations. This is the perfect time to experiment and roll out new tools to make learning meaningful for students who cannot attend campuses. This is a chance to be more efficient and productive by developing new and improved professional skills/knowledge through online learning and assessment.

The Covid-19 pandemic has created problems and disruptions in the higher education sector; campuses have closed and face-to-face teaching and assessment have moved online. It is also a fact that the use of technology in education leads to the emergence of different concepts in the system, for example, to the transition from teacher-centered education to student-centered education.

Lessons learned by institutions and students' experiences with distance learning during the pandemic will shape students' future expectations for learning, teaching and assessment, highlighting the need for universities to focus on their unique strengths in a competitive marketplace. The pandemic has created serious problems in the daily activities of education.

Physical learning is an innovative approach to learning that combines digital learning with hands-on learning and instructor-led intervention to provide a unique, engaging and inclusive learning experience for learners.

The transition to distance learning and online classes has revealed conflicting preferences; even though they wanted more interactive lectures, only half of the students were comfortable communicating with video cameras. Free text responses provided insight into how some students reported inadequate home workspace/environments and lack of essential items such as a desk, highlighting how teleworking can exacerbate social and digital divides, especially for students from poorer households. The broader negative experiences of isolation included dissatisfaction with access to health care, decreased concentration, sleep problems, and worsening mental well-being. Future education strategies will need to take into account the mental health needs of students affected by the pandemic.

2.1 Literature Review

The physical method of education has developed quite recently. Screen-based interactive devices are an effective support for the gaming learning process for children with special educational needs. (J. Goretti et al., 2020). A.A. Michael. et.al., (2021) explores the features of the interaction of consumers and sellers as part of their interaction in the physical environment. "Physical" or physical plus digital is a combination of physical circumstances or material objects and digital or online technologies. Quigley, D. (2016). Problem-based learning, competency-based learning, thought-based learning are all possible with innovative learning strategies. Some innovative learning strategies are described. Sumati, D. (2022).

Education System in India

In India, there have always been problems with the provision of education due to the lack of access. This was exacerbated by the lack of communication. Although the Internet penetration rate is close to 50%, students in the 5-25 age group have only about 15% access. As more institutions offer online courses and many new resources emerge to improve the online model and make it a viable replacement for the traditional classroom, there is potential for change. Internet-based mobile technologies can change the course of learning and make it more accessible, personalized, cost-effective and impact-resistant. Students and teachers will benefit from this merger. Schools can change their architecture to reflect this new reality, and academia can rethink curriculum and assessment systems to reflect the changed educational environment. Technology is changing our shared aspirations for quality education for all and improved learning outcomes. Access to technology and the Internet is a basic need and is no longer a luxury. The transition to distance learning has not only provided new ways of teaching and assessment, but also encourages self-learning.

Not everyone believes that online education is an equal replacement for traditional learning, but a hybrid model may become widespread in the future. The blended learning format redefines the traditional education paradigm and positively impacts the four main equations in the process: teacher-student; student-student; parent-student and parent-teacher. All four equations are regenerated as a new coupled model is developed.

2.2 National Education Policy (NEP)

The new National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 also calls for accelerating skills-based learning through "blended learning" or "physical mode". In simple terms, physical learning is the amalgamation of physical and digital learning environments or platforms. The Phygital model of skills development could be a game changer in reimagining vocational education to be more accessible, affordable and inspiring.

- State-of-the-art physical education and assessment solutions help address some of the problems that exist in existing models.
- A growing number of training providers, technical schools, state governments, academic institutions, and other ecosystem players are using the physical model to provide advanced training.

Institutions that offer curricula in the traditional traditional model are gradually introducing interactive classroom learning using technology (such as video conferencing tools, e-learning solutions, robust LMS, etc. The new decade brings many opportunities to learn, implement and try out new approaches leading to learning the knowledge, skills and abilities of the new age. The holistic growth of each person begins with the personal and professional experience of the mind.

2.3 Proposed "physical" learning structure

The proposed learning model developed in this article focuses on the following goals:

- Improving student learning,
- Enabling personalization of learning,
- Flexibility in relations of content, time and type of delivery,
- Enumerating and continuous calculation as well as the analysis of student assessments against lesson plans,

- Expanding the work of the teacher, whose experience is used to develop more creative content and delivery mechanisms,
- Focusing on the development of measurable competencies in students at an early stage, in the educational cycle,
- Designing a targeted and individual career path for each student.

2.4 Affordable, affordable, scalable learning in a secure environment

Using technology, we can take the learning environment beyond the four walls of classrooms. Along with improved accessibility, student accessibility has also increased, allowing you to study anytime, anywhere. For institutions, the phygital model has been a blessing that allows them to go beyond their campus, delivering the same high-quality learning that benefits more eligible applicants.

2.5 Quality content with standardized delivery through the phygital model

The phygital learning and content delivery model promises standardized student learning through quality content. Content is provided on a digital platform in the form of live lectures and digital resources for self-learning, as well as effective interaction with academia and industry. At the same time, practical training sessions for hands-on learning are held in the last mile training centers and/or use the digital platform capabilities.

They are complemented by digitized teaching aids, remote observation or assessment via the Internet, interactive real-time classes with industry leaders, etc. This allows students to seamlessly access educational materials, actively participate in expert classes, provide standardized knowledge dissemination, holistic learning.

2.6 Individual Skills Training

With the physical model, students can access personalized learning based on interest and ability through adaptive learning mechanisms. Innovative flexible pedagogical structures in physical mode are designed to meet the needs of different student profiles, overcoming geographic and demographic barriers. This allows students to acquire relevant and industry-relevant skill sets with flexible learning schedules.

In addition, this model provides learners with access to hands-on assessments with personalized real-time reports and analytics for self-assessment and ongoing competency testing, highlighting opportunities for improvement. This motivates to constantly improve skills, reflecting the needs of the industry.

2.7 Readiness of students for work

Physical model training helps students develop domain skills as well as develop digital skills. Thus, through a physical model that includes work experience, professional competence, and critical employability skills, they positively influence student readiness for a professional career. This model also ensures that today's students are well-acquainted with the various learning media and are better prepared for their future careers.

2.8 A Holistic Learning Environment to Achieve Desired Outcomes

Physical education uses an end-to-end approach. From learning by accessing standardized digital content with complementary reference learning materials to learning through hands-on training; from interacting with instructors, subject matter experts from industries and peers, to accessing various assessments, certifications and job opportunities, etc. A holistic learning environment integrated with a network of last mile institutions offering hands-on experience enriches the learning experience.

The result of the phygital learning model is to increase students' interest in generating interest and motivate them to continue learning in both industry and academia. Collaboration with renowned academic institutions (namely higher education or skills training institutions), industry leaders, and content development players to provide best-in-class learning in every neighborhood through last mile learning and assessment practice centers, making it affordable every youth in the country.

At the same time, this model also helps institutions generate additional revenue streams by leveraging their existing expertise and infrastructure, while continually expanding their capabilities, leading to more sustainable operations.

2.9 Physical, digital, physical learning

The education industry has undergone major changes during the pandemic. Now, as we navigate this post-pandemic world, we are in the process of rethinking learning. The accelerated digitalization of education during the pandemic is not a reversible change. In fact, the pandemic has only accelerated the penetration of technology into learning, which eventually should have happened. The National Education Policy 2020, announced in July 2020, highlights the role of blended learning. Using digital learning in education in the most effective and efficient way, i.e. through physical learning, also known as blended learning, is a union of physical and digital learning, which experts say is the most effective form of learning. as it combines the best of both worlds. Classroom learning is important for a child's social development, while digital learning is important for instilling technology literacy and efficiency through intelligent learning mechanisms.

Physical education has become the need of the hour, and this can be said not only because of the pandemic, but also because recently the interest of students in learning new things is decreasing more than ever, and there is an insanely high dropout rate. educational institutions in the world. Today the world is developing at breakneck speed, as are the requirements to survive in it. The rigid curriculum that is taught in schools leaves students of all ages ill-equipped to grow up in this world, leaving us with a question mark, "What do we do then?" The solution to this predicament lies in Phygital Learning. A kind of training that not only helps students improve their communication skills, but also explore different career paths to be ready for tomorrow. Physical education has an opportunity to get rid of the monotony of ordinary school education by reforming education. It has the ability to create a lucrative environment that inspires every student to innovate, enhancing their skills and generating much-needed curiosity about everyday learning. It is undeniable that with the introduction of digital tools, the assimilation of skills and knowledge by students has remained high compared to what they could have received only with the traditional way of learning.

3.1 Discussion

Physical learning concepts are still underway and are viewed as a work in progress by those who embrace any relevant or useful advanced technologies and/or ideas that support deeper and superior psychomotor learning. The various unique items and skills that each phygital dimension attributes to its uniqueness will influence and create an improved bridge to learning in the practical dimension. For example, many important factors such as the strategy, structure, systems, style and staff of an institution must be considered during the preparation phase of any physical projects. Technology-related learning facilities and infrastructure will play an important role in successfully positioning physical education in a pedagogical environment.

4.1 Conclusion

The concept of physical education can be applied to serve many aspects of education such as public relations for mass communication, however this article is limited to the specific subject of education. Physical education was designed to improve the quality and effectiveness of learning, especially in the field of psychomotor skills, which require extensive practice to form a tangible and developed skill. The smart learning ecosystem format in the 21st century cannot be realized on the basis of a single educational component, but requires combining the highlights of physical and digital approaches together, has endless potentials in terms of motivating learning. This paper offers input to this emerging field and provides a framework to consider as an alternative approach to problem solving when certain subjects may use limited digital content that may not be effective in terms of learning and teaching. In the near future, physical education will be expanded and made available to educators given its dynamic growth, which includes cutting-edge technology and can empower and rejuvenate education in several ways.

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